

NEANIAS
**Novel EOSC services for Emerging Atmosphere,
Underwater and Space Challenges**

Deliverable

Deliverable: D7.8 Operation Activities Report (final)

31/10/2022

NEANIAS is funded by European Union under Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme via grant agreement No. 863448

D7.8 Operation Activities Report (final)

Document Info

Project Information			
Acronym	NEANIAS		
Name	Novel EOSC Services for Emerging Atmosphere, Underwater & Space Challenges		
Start Date	01 Oct 2022	End Date	31 Oct 2022
Program	H2020-EU.1.4.1.3. - Development, deployment and operation of ICT-based e-infrastructures		
Call ID	H2020-INFRAEOSC-2018-2020	Topic	H2020-INFRAEOSC-2019-1
Grant No	863448	Instrument	RIA
Document Information			
Deliverable No	D7.8		
Deliverable Title	Operation Activities Report (final)		
Due Date	31-OCT-2022	Delivery Date	17-NOV-2022
Lead Beneficiary	GARR		
Beneficiaries (part.)	NKUA, INAF, SZTAKI, CORONIS, CITE, UOP, TELEDYNE, UNIMIB, JACOBSUNI, MEE0, GARR, ALTEC		
Editor(s)	Claudio Pisa (GARR)		
Authors (s)	Nikos Chondros (NKUA), Claudio Pisa (GARR), Konstantinos Kakalettris (CITE), Giorgos Papanikos (CITE), Attila Farkas (SZTAKI), Laura Vettorello (MEE0), Gergely Sipos (SZTAKI), Jozsef Kovacs (SZTAKI), Eva Sciacca (INAF)		
Contributor (s)	Alex Barchiesi (GARR), Efstratios Giannopoulos (CITE), Spyros Boutsis (CITE), Tziotzios Diamantis (CITE), Georgios Kakalettris (CITE), Agapios Avramidis (CITE), Michalis Konstantopoulos (NKUA), Marco Lorini (GARR), Francesco Lombardo (GARR)		
Reviewer(s)	Christos Evangelidis (NOA)		
Workpackage No	WP7 – Delivery		
Version	v1	Stage	Final
Version details	Revision: 869 . Last save: 2022-11-17, 18:36 Pages: 45 . Characters: 56.095		
Distribution	Public	Type	Report
Keywords	Delivery, EOSC, Quality metrics, operation, monitoring		

Change Record

version	Date	Change Description	Editor	Change Location (page/section)
1	17/11/2022	Document Version submitted to EC	Claudio Pisa	

Disclaimer

NEANIAS is a Research and Innovation Action funded by European Union under Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme, via grant agreement No. 863448.

NEANIAS is project that comprehensively addresses the 'Prototyping New Innovative Services' challenge set out in the 'Roadmap for EOSC' foreseen actions. It drives the co-design, delivery, and integration into EOSC of innovative thematic services, derived from state-of-the-art research assets and practices in three major sectors: underwater research, atmospheric research and space research. In each sector it engages a diverse set of research and business groups, practices, and technologies and will not only address its community-specific needs but will also enable the transition of the respective community to the EOSC concept and Open Science principles. NEANIAS provides its communities with plentiful resource access, collaboration instruments, and interdisciplinary research mechanisms, which will amplify and broaden each community's research and knowledge generation activities. NEANIAS delivers a rich set of services, designed to be flexible and extensible, able to accommodate the needs of communities beyond their original definition and to adapt to neighboring cases, fostering reproducibility and re-usability. NEANIAS identifies promising, cutting-edge business cases across several user communities and lays out several concrete exploitation opportunities.

This document has been produced receiving funding from the European Commission. The content of this document is a product of the NEANIAS project Consortium and it does not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Commission. The editor, author, contributors and reviewers of this document have taken any available measure in order for its content to be accurate and lawful. However, neither the project consortium as a whole nor the individual partners

that implicitly or explicitly participated in the creation and publication of this document may be held responsible for any damage, financial or other loss or any other issue that may arise as a result of using the content of this document or any of the project outputs that this document may refer to.

The European Union (EU) was established in accordance with the Treaty on the European Union (Maastricht). There are currently 28 member states of the European Union. It is based on the European Communities and the member states' cooperation in the fields of Common Foreign and Security Policy and Justice and Home Affairs. The five main institutions of the European Union are the European Parliament, the Council of Ministers, the European Commission, the Court of Justice, and the Court of Auditors (<http://europa.eu.int/>).

Table of Contents

Document Info	2
Change Record	3
Disclaimer	4
Table of Contents	5
Table of Figures	7
Abstract	8
1. Introduction	9
1.1. Context	9
1.2. Contents and Rationale	9
1.3. Differences from Deliverable D7.5	9
1.4. Structure of the Document	9
2. Operation Activities	10
2.1. Service Deployment	10
2.1.1. <i>Development, Staging and Production environments</i>	10
2.1.2. <i>Service deployment models</i>	10
2.1.3. <i>Primary Deployment Targets</i>	12
2.2. Operational services support activities	15
2.2.1. <i>Service Management System</i>	15
2.2.2. <i>NEANIAS Gitlab and Open-Source code</i>	16
<i>Read The Docs</i>	17
2.2.3. <i>DNS Operations</i>	17
2.2.4. <i>PKI Operations</i>	18
2.2.5. <i>Backups</i>	18
2.3. Monitoring and alerting	19
2.3.1. <i>NEANIAS monitoring and alerting</i>	19
2.3.2. <i>NEANIAS Health Page</i>	21
2.3.3. <i>EOSC integrated monitoring (ARGO)</i>	21
2.3.4. <i>GARR Cloud resource usage monitoring</i>	22
3. Service Operations Evolution	23
3.1. Core Service Integration	23
3.2. Software pipelines & packaging	25
3.3. Feature planning principles	27
3.4. Operational aspects	29
3.5. Open Science & User Onboarding	31
3.6. Monitoring	33
3.7. License & Terms of Use	34
4. Operational Performance	35

D7.8 Operation Activities Report (final)

4.1.	Service Users and Returning users.....	35
4.2.	Latency of HTTP requests.....	36
4.3.	Network latency.....	37
4.4.	Number of pending security updates	38
4.5.	Service reliability and availability.....	39
4.6.	Issues by external users	40
4.7.	Turnaround time for issues initiated by NEANIAS internal users	41
4.8.	Release cycle duration	42
5.	Conclusions.....	43
	References	44
	List of acronyms	45

Table of Figures

Figure 2.1 - S1 service, OpenNebula template.	13
Figure 2.2 - S1 service, OpenNebula template (disk).	13
Figure 2.3 - NEANIAS Gitlab dashboard screenshot	16
Figure 2.4 - NEANIAS monitoring architecture diagram	19
Figure 2.5 - Juju deployment diagram	20
Figure 2.6 - NEANIAS health page screenshot	21
Figure 3.1 - Core Service Integration: AAI	24
Figure 3.2 - Core Service Integration: Accounting	24
Figure 3.3 - Core Service Integration: Logging	24
Figure 3.4 - Core Service Integration: Catalogue	24
Figure 3.5 - Version Control System used for code base	26
Figure 3.6 - Packaged using cloud friendly technologies	26
Figure 3.7 - Continuous Integration methodologies applied	26
Figure 3.8 - Continuous Deployment methodologies applied	26
Figure 3.9 - Acceptance criteria documented	28
Figure 3.10 - Security by Design	28
Figure 3.11 - Security tests applied	28
Figure 3.12 - Secure handling & transfer data	28
Figure 3.13 - Service operating in high availability	30
Figure 3.14 - Log Management	30
Figure 3.15 - Latest version of underpinning services	30
Figure 3.16 - SMS operations followed	30
Figure 3.17 - Capacity Building material available	32
Figure 3.18 - Ticketing & helpdesk used	32
Figure 3.19 - FAIR data handling	32
Figure 3.20 - Service monitored and KPIs identified	33
Figure 3.21 - Service Operational without problems	33
Figure 3.22 - License compatible with usage	34
Figure 3.23 - Terms of Usage available to end users	34
Figure 4.1 - Service Users	35
Figure 4.2 – Monthly average and max response times of HTTP requests for October 2022 based on NEANIAS Nagios and Grafana	37
Figure 4.3 – Network Latency check on AAI host from NEANIAS Nagios	38
Figure 4.4 – Virtual machine check for security updates from NEANIAS Nagios	38
Figure 4.5 – Reliability per service for October 2022	39
Figure 4.6.- Thematic service Access request tickets	40
Figure 4.7. - Core service tickets	41
Figure 4.8. - Core service ticket first response time	41
Figure 4.9.- Average release cycle duration	42

Abstract

This document, deliverable D7.8 “Operation Activities Report (final)”, reports on the operation activities of the project and their performance regarding targets set and updates deliverable D7.5 “Operation Activities Report (interim)”. It addresses the activities concerning NEANIAS thematic and core service deployment, monitoring and support. Moreover, this document reports on the metrics and tools aimed at assessing service performance.

1. Introduction

1.1. Context

WP7 “Services Delivery and Operation” supports the NEANIAS Service delivery and operation by interacting with i) WP8 for the EOSC integration, ii) the thematic work packages WP2, WP3 and WP4 as adapted to the business cases through WP5, and iii) the core services established by WP6.

1.2. Contents and Rationale

One of the objectives of WP7 is to provide in operation the NEANIAS services, to their corresponding end-users on resources capable to deliver the required quality of service. This document, deliverable D7.8, “Operation Activities Report (final)”, updates D7.5, “Operation Activities Report (interim)” [4] and addresses the operation activities of the project and their performance regarding targets set, which stem from the work performed mainly in tasks T7.3 “Operational services provisioning” and T7.5 “Services technical assessment”. The underlying integrated infrastructures are described in deliverable D7.4, while the tools employed for the delivery tasks are described in deliverables D7.1 [1] and D7.3 [2].

Moreover, other related information on latest deployment and releases can be found in deliverables D2.8 [17], D3.8 [21], D4.8 [25], D6.8 [30], which contain information on thematic and core service releases.

1.3. Differences from Deliverable D7.5

This document, deliverable D7.8 “Operation Activities Report (final)”, updates and evolves deliverable D7.5 “Operation Activities Report (interim)”. A new section, “Services Operation Evolution” has been added, focusing on the assessment of the evolution of NEANIAS services over time, from a non-technical standpoint. The Section “Operational Performance” has been updated with the latest data. New sections have been added for EGI ACE and the NEANIAS Health Page. Moreover, all the sections of the document have been revised and updated as needed.

1.4. Structure of the Document

The document is partitioned in three main sections. Section 2, “Operation Activities” reports on the performed and ongoing activities concerning service deployment environments, service deployment models and service operation and monitoring. Section 3 “Service Operations Evolution” reports on the periodic assessment of the NEANIAS thematic and core services from a non-developer point of view, while Section 4 “Operational Performance” focuses instead on the collection and analysis of service delivery metrics.

2. Operation Activities

2.1. Service Deployment

2.1.1. Development, Staging and Production environments

In the NEANIAS AAI service, we have segregated three different realms, and we provide for three corresponding deployment environments:

- **Development (DNS subdomain “dev”):** This is an integration environment where partners deploy the latest version of their services, after they have passed their internal testing, to provide visibility to “outsiders”, i.e., people outside the core development team. This is also an “integration testing” release environment, as API providing services are first deployed here to be tested by external actors (service consumers). Due to scarcity of resources, we have agreed that each partner will host services running under the development environment on his/her own infrastructure but will make such services available 24/7 so that other partners or external actors (such as business domain users) can test their own software against newer releases of services.
- **Staging (DNS subdomain “staging”):** For services running under Kubernetes, we have deployed a separate Kubernetes cluster in the GARR Cloud with fewer nodes than the production one but identical configuration. This provides the opportunity to service providers to deploy their services in the staging environment first, and test that everything is working as expected.
- **Production (no DNS subdomain):** This is the production deployment environment for all services. For the ones running under Kubernetes, a cluster is available on top of OpenStack that is closely monitored by the GARR team for meeting its availability guarantees. For special use cases another Kubernetes cluster was made available by CITE, hosted at NKUA. Additionally, a 3rd managed Kubernetes cluster was also added, coming from EGI ACE. For services that deploy using VMs, each service provider manages their own set of VMs that comprise their corresponding service. These VMs reside either at GARR or at CESNET’s OpenStack, the latter coming again from EGI ACE (see Section 2.1.3.1 for details). Finally, a bare-metal based Kubernetes cluster was also available, mostly for Machine Learning deployments, but we discouraged its use and proposed the use of the OpenStack based one during the second term of the project. This cluster was eventually phased-out.

2.1.2. Service deployment models

2.1.2.1. Virtual Machine deployment

Deliverable D7.4 “Infrastructures integration report (interim)” [3] and Deliverable D7.7 “Infrastructures integration report” [5], describe the infrastructures employed by the NEANIAS services. NEANIAS service providers can employ IaaS platforms based on OpenStack and OpenNebula to create virtual machines, consuming compute and storage resources.

This approach may leverage platform-specific cloud facilities, such as platform-specific load balancers and firewalls, the drawback being the decreased portability of the service to different cloud infrastructures.

2.1.2.2. Kubernetes Deployment

For services that deploy using Kubernetes, continuous integration can be achieved using Gitlab's functionality. NEANIAS has its own Gitlab instance (deployed under gitlab.neanias.eu). The main component of the process is a Gitlab runner, which executes unit and integration tests, builds Docker images, and, finally, deploys the service on the target environment.

NEANIAS Gitlab provides a "shared" runner, which any service can use to perform operations such as building docker images and executing tests. However, to allow a runner to deploy the service in a specific environment, e.g., the "dev" subdomain, each partner deploys a private runner, in the same Kubernetes cluster and namespace that the service is deployed, so that the runner has access to the cluster's resources, under the service provider's access rights.

Using the above tools and conventions, one of the policies that can be adopted by service providers that are deploying to the production Kubernetes cluster is the following:

1. Use the provided "shared" runner for any step of the process that does not require access to the resources of a specific deployment environment.
2. Create a Gitlab runner in each Kubernetes cluster that the service provider is using. These runners are tagged under Gitlab with the name of the corresponding environment (development, staging and production).
3. Use feature branches to develop new features, create bug fixes and document the changes in a changelog.
4. Use merge requests to integrate changes of these features to the master branch.
5. Create a Gitlab pipeline action to execute tests of the service upon creating a merge request to master branch, and accept the merge request only when all tests succeed.
6. Release the service to the development environment:
 - a. Create a new Gitlab release with semantic versioning.
 - b. Setup the shared runner to build a new docker image, tag it with the version number of the release, and push it to the container registry of the service.
 - c. Setup the development runner to deploy the new release to the development environment.
 - d. Setup the shared runner to execute integration tests with the remaining NEANIAS services on the development environment.
7. Potentially create a new round of User Acceptance testing from a broader audience than the core development team.
8. Use merge requests to the production branch, to integrate new releases to staging and production environments.
9. Release the service to the staging environment:
 - a. Setup the staging runner to deploy the new release to the staging environment when merging from master to production branch.
 - b. Potentially setup the shared runner to execute integration tests on the staging environment.
 - c. Verify integration with components that are identical to the production environment.
10. Release the service to the production environment:
 - a. Setup production runner to deploy the new release to the production environment, after manual verification of the staging environment.

2.1.2.3. Linux containers

Linux containers are a type of lightweight operating system level virtualization, in which different containers share the same operating system kernel.

In particular, Docker containers [6] offer a popular way to package and deliver applications, and are widely supported by different platforms.

While Docker containers are oriented towards application packaging to implement microservices applications, and tend to minimize the image sizes to include only the strictly needed dependencies, LXC containers [7] address the need for full operating system virtualization, where several applications are running on the same system.

Please note that for what concerns NEANIAS services, Linux containers are deployed either in virtual machines or in Kubernetes clusters (where they are placed in *Pods*, i.e. groups of containers).

2.1.3. Primary Deployment Targets

This section describes, from a service delivery perspective, the main infrastructures where the production deployments are targeted. For a complete list of the infrastructural resources leveraged by the NEANIAS project please refer to deliverable D7.7 “Infrastructures Integration Report” [5].

2.1.3.1. GARR Cloud

Most of the NEANIAS services rely on the GARR Cloud as their underlying infrastructure. To ensure access to the GARR Cloud IaaS and PaaS resources the GARR Cloud administrators perform the following tasks:

- Partition the compute and storage resources in different OpenStack projects and Kubernetes namespaces, setting the appropriate quotas for storage and computing resources
- Accept NEANIAS user registrations to the GARR Cloud and assign them to the appropriate OpenStack projects and namespaces. The registration (and login) can be performed through three supported authentication methods:
 1. IDEM/eduGAIN (SAML)
 2. Google (OIDC)
 3. Form registration
- Notify the users that they can access the GARR Cloud facilities and provide them with instructions and documentation

The GARR Cloud support can be contacted via e-mail at the address cloud-support@garr.it, which automatically creates tickets in the GARR ticketing system.

Concerning the security procedures of the GARR Cloud team, these are certified ISO/IEC 27001.

2.1.3.2. OpenNebula deployment

In the NEANIAS project, the MEEC Cloud offers the virtual resources in an OpenNebula instance. The deployment process goes through some preliminary steps such as the definition of a template. Figure 2.1 and Figure 2.2 show an example for the S1 services, in the context of Work Package 4.

D7.8 Operation Activities Report (final)

Update VM Template 91 explorer-space-dev oneadmin OpenNebula

Update Wizard Advanced

General Storage Network OS Booting Input/Output Actions Context Scheduling Hybrid

VM Group Other

Name: explorer-space-dev

Description:

Hypervisor: KVM vCenter

Logo:

Memory: 8 GB Cost: 0,00 COST / MONTH

Memory modification: any value

CPU: 2 Cost: 0,00 COST / MONTH

CPU modification: any value

VCPU: 2

VCPU modification: any value

Figure 2.1 - S1 service, OpenNebula template.

The template's requirements should be defined in collaboration with the service provider. This process has to define:

- required memory and CPU;
- one or more virtual networks and their policies;
- a set of disks with persistent images;
- optional attributes that could be useful for the deployment.

Update VM Template 91 explorer-space-dev oneadmin OpenNebula

Update Wizard Advanced

General **Storage** Network OS Booting Input/Output Actions Context Scheduling Hybrid

VM Group Other

Disk 0 Image Volatile disk

You selected the following image: explorer-space-dev

Figure 2.2 - S1 service, OpenNebula template (disk).

The templates are persistent, it means they are stored in the system for future reuse.

D7.8 Operation Activities Report (final)

The network interfaces are defined like other resources needed by the VM. This type of automatic selection can recognise the required network type and it will be automatically selected among those available in the cluster.

After the template definition, the deployment goes ahead with the effective resources' allocation and the needed configuration. After that, the service provider will be able to connect to the OpenNebula resource and to deploy the service by its own procedure.

At the current status, there aren't any services deployed via Docker in the MEEO OpenNebula instance. However, it has a dedicated client to manage Docker containers and also native features for this objective, therefore this kind of deployment could be potentially supported.

2.1.3.3. EGI ACE

During the last year of the project, NEANIAS gained access to EGI resources than to the EGI ACE call where the project applied and got accepted. We were assigned to CESNET, the EGI member on the Czech Republic, which provided us access to the following resources:

1. At the OpenStack level:
 - a. CPU: 172
 - b. RAM: 416 GB
 - c. GPU: 13
 - d. Disks: 14 TB
2. At the Kubernetes level:
 - a. CPU: 252
 - b. RAM: 1300 GB
 - c. GPU: 15
 - d. Disks: 47 TB

Thus, NEANIAS has services deployed at CESNET's OpenStack, which gave us access to GPU resources lacking at GARR.

Additionally, NEANIAS also has services deployed at the managed Kubernetes offering of CESNET. This is a new approach to infrastructure management, where the resource provider is also the sole administrator of the cluster, thus alleviating the need for systems-level administration from the service providers. Again, GPUs are also available at the Kubernetes level.

2.2. Operational services support activities

2.2.1. Service Management System

The NEANIAS Service Management System (SMS) is based on the Redmine ticketing system deployed as a Docker container. The backend database was implemented as a MySQL database and deployed in a Docker container as well. The NEANIAS SMS integrated with the NEANIAS AAI for authentication and minimal authorization for admin access. There are two different versions of the SMS system, development and production version with different backend databases. The development version can be deployed via a docker compose for local development purposes. The production version is deployed in the production Kubernetes cluster with reverse proxy and HTTPS functionality and integrated with NEANIAS AAI in the production realm. The production database is deployed on the GARR Cloud platform as a docker container with manual backups.

The procedures described in Deliverable D8.2 [8] are implemented in the SMS system, with additional internal procedures. The FitSM procedures are realized with custom Redmine trackers and workflows. In addition, the SMS automatically supports ticket assignment based on the ticket's content. This automation is implemented with the Custom workflows Redmine plugin with Ruby scripts. Based on the ticket assignment, e-mail notifications will be sent to the corresponding project members. Critical tickets can be submitted to ensure quicker response from the assigned project member. The whole SMS system is documented on Redmine Wiki pages which is publicly reachable after the login.

The SMS supports the following Procedures:

- **Access Request:** As part of the Customer Relationship Management process, the users can request access to the different Thematic services and to selected Core services. Some service requires custom fields for the access request; therefore, different access request trackers are implemented based on the same workflow.
- **Question:** As part of the Customer Relationship Management process, the users can submit general questions regarding the different Thematic services. This process provides the general Helpdesk functionality for the Thematic services.
- **Complaint:** As part of the Customer Relationship Management process, the users can submit complaints regarding the different Thematic services.
- **Incident:** As part of the Incident and service request management, the users can submit incidents regarding the different Thematic services.
- **Internal request:** As part of the Incident and service request management, the NEANIAS project members can report any incident or request regarding the Core or Thematic services. For example, the certification request for the NEANIAS Logging service is implemented as part of the internal request workflow.
- **Maintenance:** As part of the Incident and service request management, the NEANIAS project members can report any maintenance period regarding the Core or Thematic services. Every project member will be notified via email, and the service providers can decide whether their services are affected or not and report following maintenance periods if necessary (ripple effect).
- **Change Request:** As part of the Change management, the users can submit a change request to the different Thematic services. The goal of this process is to ensure changes to the Thematic services.

D7.8 Operation Activities Report (final)

- Improvement request: As part of the Continual service improvement management, the users can submit improvement requests to the different Thematic services. This procedure aims to identify and exploit opportunities for improvement of the Thematic service.

The Thematic services can integrate these procedures with premade links for the services with pre-filled fields. These links can be published on the service websites, in the EOSC and NEANIAS Catalogue as well.

2.2.2. NEANIAS Gitlab and Open-Source code

The NEANIAS Gitlab is available to NEANIAS partners at gitlab.neanias.eu. It supports service development and deployment through CI/CD facilities. The NEANIAS Gitlab supports the NEANIAS AAI for authentication. When a user performs the access to the NEANIAS Gitlab through the NEANIAS AAI, a new Gitlab user is created. By default, this newly created user will be in the “blocked” status, and will not be able to perform any tasks. The Gitlab administrator performs the task of unblocking these users and assigning them to groups and Gitlab projects. Figure 2.3 shows a screenshot of the NEANIAS Gitlab featuring statistics such as the number of users, projects and groups at the time of writing.

Figure 2.3 - NEANIAS Gitlab dashboard screenshot

Please note that the software released and published by the project with an open-source license (some of which is hosted on the NEANIAS Gitlab) is indexed at <https://source.neanias.eu/>

Read The Docs

As reported in Deliverables D7.1 [1], D7.2 [11] and D7.4 [3], the NEANIAS services documentation is hosted by *Read the Docs* (<https://readthedocs.org>). When a service provider, who already has a documentation git repository in the NEANIAS Gitlab, expresses the need for documentation hosting the following steps are performed:

1. A new Read the Docs project is created as a subproject of the main NEANIAS project. The name of the new Read the Docs project is returned to the service provider
2. A webhook is created in Read the Docs, linked to the Git repository hosting the service documentation. The Webhook URL is returned to the service provider
3. The service provider adds the webhook URL returned from step 2 to the webhooks of the Gitlab project hosting the service documentation Git repository. This webhook should be triggered when a new commit is pushed to the repository
4. The service provider edits the root documentation Git repository to add a link to their service documentation, using the service identifier yielded in step 1.

Service providers are not required to have an account at Read the Docs, but they might wish to do so to configure advanced options (e.g. documentation localization options).

2.2.3. DNS Operations

The NEANIAS DNS contains DNS records of NEANIAS services that need to have a public fully qualified name (FQDN) or special DNS records (i.e. TXT records, MX records, etc).

DNS records are created on the first deployment of a service, after a request from the service provider to the NEANIAS DNS zone administrators (managed by CITE). Records can be altered, if needed, following the same procedure, in case the service needs to be accessible using another IP or proxy.

The following naming convention is followed (§ Section 2.1.1):

- For services running in the production environment, the main domain name is used for creating the related DNS records, i.e. <service>.neanias.eu
- For services running in the staging environment a subdomain named staging.neanias.eu is used (i.e. <service>.staging.neanias.eu.
- For services running in the development environment a subdomain named staging.neanias.eu is used (i.e. <service>.dev.neanias.eu.

If the service is accessed directly through a dedicated public IP then a type A DNS record is used. If the service is running behind a proxy then a DNS record of type CNAME is used, pointing to the related proxy.

In the cases where a proxy or a service is served by many nodes, multiple DNS records may be created for the same service, using the corresponding IP address for each service node, to achieve DNS load balancing.

Currently in the neanias.eu zone there are 55 DNS records for Production (including 4 for neanias email), 18 DNS records for Staging and 26 DNS records for Development. DNS zone is managed by the DNS administrators through a user interface with restricted access. DNS names of interest to the public are listed in the NEANIAS Catalogue [9].

2.2.4. PKI Operations

NEANIAS public key infrastructure (PKI) is used for the creation, storage and revocation of digital certificates which are used to verify that a particular public key belongs to a certain NEANIAS service. It is used for creating certificates only for NEANIAS services. These certificates are used for encryption/authentication/authorization between NEANIAS services. The NEANIAS PKI is deployed on CITE's infrastructure and the activities taking place by its administrators are:

- Creation of a certificate: the NEANIAS PKI is signing certificate signing requests that are sent to NEANIAS PKI administration by NEANIAS service providers.
- Storage of issued certificates: all issued certificates are stored in the PKI and can be sent again to the service provider at any point, if needed.
- Certificate renewal (same private key): At any point, a service provider may request for a renewal of a certificate. At this stage, the service provider may ask for a "subject" change too. The renewal of a certificate is not requiring a new certificate request.
- Re-issue a certificate: re-issuing is required when the service provider needs to change the private key of the service. For example, if the key is lost or compromised. In that case the previous certificates are being revoked and a new one is created.
- Certificate revocation: Is taking place when a service provider informs the NEANIAS PKI that a key is decommissioned or was stolen or was changed. In that case the certificates for this key are revoked.
- Revocation list creation: Each time a certificate is revoked a new Certificate Revocation List (CRL) is created and then is posted on ca.neanias.eu
 - http://ca.neanias.eu/crl/neanias_ca.crl
 - http://ca.neanias.eu/crl/neanias_root_ca.crl

2.2.5. Backups

All information available as "volumes" in OpenStack at GARR is backed by the Ceph filesystem, which guarantees triple redundancy. As such, we are certain that there are no single points of failure in the storage layer.

However, this does not constitute a proper backup policy, as it does not protect against human errors, or more severe multiple-machine failure situations.

To address this, each service provider is facilitated with what is offered by WP7 to design and implement his/her own backup policy, to satisfy business continuity needs as required by their respective SLAs.

For some infrastructural services, such as Gitlab and the monitoring systems, regular snapshots of the OpenStack volumes are performed. These snapshots add redundancy and can be used to recover the systems in case of accidental data loss.

2.3. Monitoring and alerting

2.3.1. NEANIAS monitoring and alerting

Monitoring is the key service needed to gain insights into an infrastructure. It needs to be continuous and on-demand to quickly detect, correlate, and analyse data for a fast reaction to anomalous behaviour. The challenge of this type of monitoring is how to quickly identify and correlate problems before they affect end-users and ultimately the productivity of their organizations. The features of a monitoring system are monitoring of services, reporting availability and reliability, visualization of the services status, providing dashboard interfaces and sending real-time alerts. Management teams, administrators, service owners can monitor the availability and reliability of the services from a high-level view down to individual system metrics and monitor the conformance of multiple SLAs.

The NEANIAS monitoring infrastructure has been deployed through the Juju automation tool in the GARR Cloud. It is composed by the following components:

- Nagios - a monitoring and alerting system
- NRPE (Nagios Remote plugin executor) - an agent to execute Nagios probes on remote systems
- InfluxDB - a time series database
- Nagflux – a metrics collector from Nagios to InfluxDB
- Grafana - a platform for data visualization, querying and alerting
- Prometheus - a monitoring and alerting tool
- Telegraf – an agent for collecting, processing, aggregating and writing metrics

Figure 2.4 - NEANIAS monitoring architecture diagram

Figure 2.4 depicts the devised monitoring and alerting architecture. The NEANIAS services deployed on virtual machines on top of *OpenStack* or *OpenNebula* are monitored through *Nagios*. *Nagflux* inserts the metrics collected by the Nagios probes in an *InfluxDB* database. NEANIAS services deployed on *Kubernetes* clusters are instead monitored through *telegraf*,

D7.8 Operation Activities Report (final)

which is responsible for sending the collected metrics to *Prometheus*. *Grafana* can then perform data visualization for data stored both in *Prometheus* and *InfluxDB*.

The infrastructure described above has been implemented as a microservices architecture composed by virtual machines and LXC containers, through the *Juju* automation system.

Figure 2.5 shows the deployed microservices (or *charms* using *Juju* terminology) and their relations.

Figure 2.5 - Juju deployment diagram

Service providers, to monitor their virtual machine based services, deploy Nagios probes (NRPE). An Ansible playbook has been provided in the NEANIAS Gitlab to automate this step. Then, to update the Nagios configuration to take into account the new service, the service provider produces a new commit in the nagios-configuration Git repository on the NEANIAS Gitlab, specifying the IP address of the NRPE probe. These commits trigger a CI/CD pipeline which checks for the correctness of the commit. If this check passes, the actual Nagios configuration is updated with the new service.

To monitor Kubernetes based services through Prometheus, service providers either expose HTTP endpoints on their applications providing Prometheus formatted metrics, or deploy a *telegraf* “sidecar” in their service pods, or else use the telegraf Kubernetes operator. Also the NEANIAS kubernetes clusters resources themselves are monitored through Prometheus.

D7.8 Operation Activities Report (final)

2.3.2. NEANIAS Health Page

To provide the users of the NEANIAS services with an overview of the status of the services, a health page has been developed and made available at <https://health.neanias.eu/>. A screenshot is shown below in Figure 2.6.

Figure 2.6 - NEANIAS health page screenshot

The shown information yields from the NEANIAS monitoring InfluxDB database (described in section 2.3.1 above), thus derives from data collected in near real time. The page, in addition to displaying the status of the service, shows scheduled maintenance periods for each service.

2.3.3. EOSC integrated monitoring (ARGO)

The EGI e-infrastructure federation provides service monitoring service in EOSC (<http://argo.eu.github.io/index.html>) based on the ARGO system. This ARGO-based Service collects service status results from monitoring engine(es) and delivers status results and/or monthly availability (A) and reliability (R) statistics of distributed services. Both the status results and A/R statistics are presented through a Web UI, with the possibility for users to drill-down from the availability of a site to individual services, to individual test results that contributed to overall reliability/availability of the service. Argo is capable also to send

D7.8 Operation Activities Report (final)

notifications to the service admins in case of a failure/warning on one of the services monitored.

ARGO Service Monitoring keeps an eye on the performance of IT services and quickly detects issues and helps the providers resolve them. With Service Monitoring service providers can get:

- the activation of monitoring for their services with minimal effort
- a ready-to-use user interface
- automated reporting tools

The NEANIAS project successfully engaged with the EGI ARGO team, yielding to the monitoring through ARGO of all the NEANIAS thematic services and of a subset of the NEANIAS core services [13]. Moreover, as also reported in deliverable D8.5 “EOSC Integration Activities Report (final)” [31], selected metrics are made available at the NEANIAS Service Catalogue [13], leveraging ARGO APIs.

2.3.4. GARR Cloud resource usage monitoring

The usage of the GARR Cloud resources employed by the NEANIAS project is periodically reviewed. This allows to accommodate the services requirements as the need arises.

For security reasons, as the operation requires administrative rights on the GARR Cloud, the resource usage collection is performed through an automated script leveraging the OpenStack command line client, but triggered manually by the GARR staff.

3. Service Operations Evolution

During the service delivery process, the methodology, characteristics, and processes applied were monitored in order to provide needed feedback as well as to make sure that the delivered services were adhering to the characteristics set forward for all NEANIAS offered services. The assessment of this monitoring activities was conducted from a non-developer standpoint but also covered non-functional assessment and evaluation of the services as perceived via processes and integrators. The information collected was then resent to the service providers to be evaluated and used as input for subsequent releases and enhancements.

Towards this end, among other assessment and enhancement iteration methodologies, across the three major software releases of the NEANIAS offerings, services were evaluated using an assessment checklist (as defined in D7.3 “Software assessment methodology” [2]). The evolution of the service evaluation is another indication on how services matured during the delivery and operations cycles they undergone within NEANIAS.

In the following section we present some selected findings that highlights the evolution of the NEANIAS services with respect to their delivery and operation. The information collected is visualized as a snapshot of the service aggregated status with respect to a topic at the time of one of the three major releases (for thematic and core services alike). The service evaluation was aggregated under two or three (depending on the topic) statuses to indicate compliance or achievement of the specific topic (achieved / partially achieved / work still ongoing). It needs to be highlighted that some services continued evolving after the third release in response to user feedback and service provider plans, so the third release snapshot may not be indicative of their current status.

The graphs presented below display the percentage of the services that correspond to the specific assessment level across the responses retrieved within each of the three major service releases. The services evaluated are across all NEANIAS offered services, including Underwater ([14], [15], [16]), Atmospheric ([18], [19], [20]), Space ([22], [23], [24]) and Core ([26], [28], [29]) Services.

3.1. Core Service Integration

The NEANIAS ecosystem is comprised of several thematic services, targeting different scientific disciplines and end users. These service base their operation on a number of core services offering reusable functionality. In the following figures we present how the integration of the NEANIAS services with a selected subset of these core services has evolved over the course of the three major releases. The selected core services include the NEANIAS AAI service (“Figure 3.1 - Core Service Integration: AAI”), the Accounting service (“Figure 3.2 - Core Service Integration: Accounting”), the Log Aggregation service (“Figure 3.3 - Core Service Integration: Logging”) and the Catalogue of services (“Figure 3.4 - Core Service Integration: Catalogue”).

It is worth noting that even since the second release, the majority of the services had completed the needed integrations, while by the third release, almost 100% of the needed integrations were finalized. Services that had not completed the integrations were primarily exposed as modules through other services acting as gateways to their functionality.

D7.8 Operation Activities Report (final)

Figure 3.1 - Core Service Integration: AAI

Figure 3.2 - Core Service Integration: Accounting

Figure 3.3 - Core Service Integration: Logging

Figure 3.4 - Core Service Integration: Catalogue

3.2. Software pipelines & packaging

One of the challenges faced and goals pursued within the NEANIAS project was that of bringing software components starting from low TRL levels to mature level of being able to be operational, cloud enabled, Open Science aligned and for some, onboard to the EOSC ecosystem. One of the starting points towards achieving these goals was to streamline the packaging and delivery aspects of the software components. In the following figures, we highlight some of the key aspects used to evaluate and steer the work of service providers in achieving this goal.

In “Figure 3.5 - Version Control System used for code base” we aggregate the information collected with respect to how a central Version Control System is used by individual service providers both to store and manage the software components code evolution as well as apply consistently a branch management system that will facilitate in the evolution of the service. Respectively, in “Figure 3.6 - Packaged using cloud friendly technologies” we aggregate the technologies used for packaging and distributing the service components using technologies that are considered cloud friendly and are supported by the infrastructures available within NEANIAS for the services to be deployed and operated.

In “Figure 3.7 - Continuous Integration methodologies applied” and “Figure 3.8 - Continuous Deployment methodologies applied” we examine the progress made by individual service providers to be able to support a CI/CD pipeline that can facilitate the streamlining of the develop-build-test-deploy pipeline. Extensive internal tutorials, guidelines, and support has been provided towards this end and although almost half of the services managed to adopt Continuous Integration approaches, the adoption of Continuous Delivery approaches proved to be harder to integrate. Given service specific requirements and priorities, but also the steep knowledge curve for some of processes and technologies involved as well as the knowhow available within service providers, the full adoption of the CI/CD methodologies was not possible.

D7.8 Operation Activities Report (final)

Figure 3.5 - Version Control System used for code base

Figure 3.6 - Packaged using cloud friendly technologies

Figure 3.7 - Continuous Integration methodologies applied

Figure 3.8 - Continuous Deployment methodologies applied

3.3. Feature planning principles

Another aspect of the monitored and evaluated aspect of the evolution of the services included the adoption of best practices early in the design of the services and software components as well as the commitment to follow up on these during the course of a service lifecycle, with appropriate actions. In the following diagrams, we pick a selected subset of these topics. Other metrics presented in this section may fall under the same category of evaluation but are used to indicate additional considerations.

In “Figure 3.9 - Acceptance criteria documented” we present the approach of Service Providers towards documenting and defining early in the process of Service feature development the acceptance criteria by which the feature would be considered successfully included and integrated.

In “Figure 3.10 - Security by Design” we present the aggregated responses of Service Providers indicating the inclusion of security aspects early in the design process, including targeting vulnerabilities from outdated dependencies (see also “Figure 3.15 - Latest version of underpinning services”), authentication safeguards and best programming practices. In “Figure 3.11 - Security tests applied” and “Figure 3.12 - Secure handling & transfer data” we present how the security aspect is followed up during the testing phase as well as at operation and system configuration time, with services being tested for known security vulnerabilities (unauthorized access to resources, input validation, etc) and configured in order to safely handle data in transit (secure socket layer), handle sensitive data securely (where applies) and monitoring to ensure that no known critical level vulnerability is unhandled.

D7.8 Operation Activities Report (final)

Figure 3.9 - Acceptance criteria documented

Figure 3.10 - Security by Design

Figure 3.11 - Security tests applied

Figure 3.12 - Secure handling & transfer data

3.4. Operational aspects

With respect to other operational aspects of the services, a number of parameters had to be examined and continuously improved to ensure that the services remained both operational as well as continuously available and reachable by end users and integrating services. Some aspects that were evaluated and were subsequently provided as feedback to service providers are presented in the following statistics.

In “Figure 3.13 - Service operating in high availability” we present the aggregated view of services which have been deployed and remain operational under a high availability scheme that ensures continuous operation of the service in cases of arbitrary system or hardware failure, giving time to its operators to be notified and react respectively. Similarly, for a service provider to be able to identify failure causes but also to be able to monitor the state and well behavior of its offering, proper log management and log entry handling as presented in “Figure 3.14 - Log Management” is important. This may include consistent log keeping, rotation of logs, safe log storage, proper usage of available resources for the log maintenance, etc.

In an environment as diverse as the one comprised by the NEANIAS services, the Service Management processes assist in maintaining agreed best practices but also to document and assist in the everyday management of each individual service as well as the infrastructure in general. For this purpose, the usage and conformance to the SMS processes and operations defined, as depicted in “Figure 3.16 - SMS operations followed” remains of high importance and was one of the primary focuses of the delivery work package, following also the guidelines coming from EOSC. During the evolution of each service, it remained critical for the dependency management of services reusing other offering to be able to evolve and stay up to date with the latest stable version of its underpinning services. The available infrastructure separation (dev / staging / production) was used for the purpose in order to timely test integration changes and service remain current in their dependencies as presented in “Figure 3.15 - Latest version of underpinning services”.

D7.8 Operation Activities Report (final)

Figure 3.13 - Service operating in high availability

Figure 3.14 - Log Management

Figure 3.15 - Latest version of underpinning services

Figure 3.16 - SMS operations followed

3.5. Open Science & User Onboarding

Towards achieving the goal of providing EOSC aligned services that can facilitate researchers to take advantage but also to contribute to Open Science, as well as make the services easy to be used and streamline the onboarding process for new users, individual service providers and NEANIAS as a whole took a number of steps and initiatives. In this section we do not list all the actions taken but we do report on how the service evolved in order to facilitate this goal from the perspective that falls under the delivery processes.

To enable the onboarding process, a lot of focus has been given by all service providers to make available training and onboarding material in various forms, as best suiting each case. Emphasis has been given for the material to remain available and relevant for the long term usage of the service and as shown in “Figure 3.17 - Capacity Building material available”, this process has started early in the services lifecycle, expanding to include more in depth material and in additional forms.

To ease the end-users utilizing the various NEANIAS services as well as intra-service communications, a central entry point for the user requests was created to handle the ticketing and the services Helpdesk. The adoption by service providers was progressive and gradually included more aspects, starting from intra-service communication and continuing to end-user support under the Helpdesk processes as shown in “Figure 3.18 - Ticketing & helpdesk used”.

Another important aspect towards the Open Science and EOSC goals is for services to facilitate FAIR data management, as this applies to each individual domain and service functionalities. Towards this, services were evaluated based on the capabilities they offer in order to facilitate the discovery, usage and publication of relevant research products in the respective catalogues, where applicable, as shown in “Figure 3.19 - FAIR data handling”.

D7.8 Operation Activities Report (final)

Figure 3.17 - Capacity Building material available

Figure 3.18 - Ticketing & helpdesk used

Figure 3.19 - FAIR data handling

3.6. Monitoring

Yet another important aspect related to the service level that individual services can offer to their end users is that of monitoring the behavior and proper operation of the service. To that end, NEANIAS has provided multiple solutions to enable both internal tracking as well as external, EOSC-service based monitoring. The aggregated status of the services monitoring level is presented in the following “Figure 3.20 - Service monitored and KPIs identified” and utilizing these facilities, the operational status of the services are shown in “Figure 3.21 - Service Operational without problems”.

Figure 3.20 - Service monitored and KPIs identified

Figure 3.21 - Service Operational without problems

3.7. License & Terms of Use

Finally, another important topic on which the services were being monitored and assessed on during the course of their delivery process was the availability of the proper licensing information as well as the Terms of Use being available to end users, where applicable.

Figure 3.22 - License compatible with usage

Figure 3.23 - Terms of Usage available to end users

4. Operational Performance

The operational performance of the NEANIAS thematic and core services is assessed against the quality metrics which are relevant for operational performance, among the set of recommended quality metrics included in Deliverable D7.1 [1] and D7.5 [4].

These metrics are assessed through the monitoring tools described in deliverable D7.1 [1], D7.2 [11], D7.3 [2] and D7.4 [3] and relevant services among the NEANIAS core services described in deliverable D6.1 [12] and D6.4 [27], namely:

- EGI ARGO - EOSC integrated monitoring (§ deliverable D7.1 [1], D7.5 [4] Section 2.3.3 of this document)
- Nagios based monitoring (§ deliverable D7.1 [1], deliverable D7.2 [11], D7.5 [4] Section 2.3.1 of his document)
- Accounting service (§ deliverable D6.1 [12] and D6.4 [27])
- Logging service (§ deliverable D6.1 [12] and D6.4 [27])
- SMS system (§ deliverable D7.3 [2], deliverable D7.4 [3], deliverable D7.7 [5])

These tools have yielded the operational performance measurements reported in the subsequent sections.

4.1. Service Users and Returning users

One of the important metrics that was monitored throughout the evolution of the NEANIAS services, to help measure and understand the impact that the services had during the onboarding process, was the *service users* count. To help monitor this metric, the NEANIAS Accounting service was utilized. This helped to identify individual user logins to services as well as service usage, based on each service accounting information.

The evolution of usage, across the three major releases and at the time of compiling this report, is presented in the following diagram “Figure 4.1 - Service Users”.

Figure 4.1 - Service Users

As it is expected, as the services were getting closer to their final version, the service usage increased both through the service validation phases, as well as the outreaching and user onboarding activities that took place. At the time of compiling this deliverable, more than

D7.8 Operation Activities Report (final)

2400 individual users had access the NEANIAS services, aggregated across all thematic and core sectors.

At this point, it is worth noting that, since the NEANIAS Accounting service was used to track the user numbers, until the point where individual services were tracking login and usage statistics in the accounting service, some early user access may not be tracked.

Supplementary to the service user number, an equally important metric is that of the *returning users*. After a user has accessed and used the NEANIAS services, accessing it again and reusing the services at a later point in time is an initial indication that the service is meeting their expectations and they find value in reusing its features.

At the time of compiling the deliverable, the returning user percentage was calculated at **36.71%**. It is worth noting that given the high increase of user onboarding activities in the last period, prior to the deliverable being compiled, new user registrations have increased, and it can be expected that the number of returning users may show significant increase in the following period.

4.2. Latency of HTTP requests

Another quality metric that is used for monitoring the performance of NEANIAS services is the *latency of HTTP requests*, which is the time from when a request is made until the time the response is received. This metric is monitored by NEANIAS Nagios and Grafana installations and from EGI ARGO and is based on the HTTP average response time of HTTP calls to the endpoints of NEANIAS services. This result is including the relevant network latency.

As displayed in Figure 4.2, the average HTTP latency during October 2022 was less than 0.5s for almost all service endpoints, which is an acceptable HTTP request latency for cloud services.

Network latency that is included in these numbers is not equal for all services, since services may be running on different physical servers, or on different datacenters or European countries than the monitoring service.

D7.8 Operation Activities Report (final)

Figure 4.2 – Monthly average and max response times of HTTP requests for October 2022 based on NEANIAS Nagios and Grafana

4.3. Network latency

Another quality metric that is being used by NEANIAS services to monitor performance is *network latency*. For network latency measurements, ICMP (i.e. ping) tests are used. Network latency is measured only when applicable. This is not affecting the overall performance measurement of the services since is already included in the time of the HTTP requests latency, as already mentioned in Section 4.2.

In some cases, the total network latency cannot be measured through ICMP. These cases include: a) when services are running on Kubernetes Clusters distributed on multiple physical servers/racks; (b) when the infrastructure where the service is running is exposing only the minimal subset of ports needed for the service operation and is not accepting ICMP requests; (c) when the services are running behind proxies or NAT. In these cases we can only check the HTTP check response time.

The network latency may vary since services may be running on different clouds/infrastructures (GARR, EGI ACE, NKUA, MEE0, CITE, etc.) than the monitoring service. In Figure 4.3 we can see a check in time for network latency from NEANIAS Nagios Service (running on GARR infrastructure) to the host that is running the NEANIAS AAI service (running on NKUA infrastructure), which is one of the cases in which the network latency is measured towards services running on different cloud infrastructures and on different countries than the monitoring service.

D7.8 Operation Activities Report (final)

The average network latency is in acceptable range for all measured cases.

Service State Information

Current Status:	OK (for 0d 3h 38m 55s)
Status Information:	PING OK - Packet loss = 0%, RTA = 44.83 ms
Performance Data:	rta=44.827000ms;3000.000000;5000.000000;0.000000 pl=0%;80;100;0
Current Attempt:	1/2 (HARD state)
Last Check Time:	2022-10-26 09:31:01
Check Type:	ACTIVE
Check Latency / Duration:	0.394 / 4.108 seconds
Next Scheduled Check:	2022-10-26 09:36:01
Last State Change:	2022-10-26 05:56:01
Last Notification:	N/A (notification 0)
Is This Service Flapping?	NO (0.00% state change)
In Scheduled Downtime?	NO
Last Update:	2022-10-26 09:34:52 (0d 0h 0m 4s ago)

Figure 4.3 – Network Latency check on AAI host from NEANIAS Nagios

4.4. Number of pending security updates

Virtual Machines are being monitored for security updates through Nagios, as shown in the next figure.

Service State Information

Current Status:	OK (for 0d 0h 4m 34s)
Status Information:	NOTE: This is only a simulation! apt-get needs root privileges for real execution. Keep also in mind that locking is deactivated, so don't depend on the relevance to the real current situation! APT OK: 0 packages available for upgrade (0 critical updates).
Performance Data:	available_upgrades=0;;;0 critical_updates=0;;;0
Current Attempt:	1/2 (HARD state)
Last Check Time:	2022-10-31 10:24:16
Check Type:	ACTIVE
Check Latency / Duration:	0.182 / 0.909 seconds
Next Scheduled Check:	2022-10-31 10:54:16
Last State Change:	2022-10-31 10:24:16
Last Notification:	N/A (notification 0)
Is This Service Flapping?	NO (6.25% state change)
In Scheduled Downtime?	NO
Last Update:	2022-10-31 10:28:43 (0d 0h 0m 7s ago)

Figure 4.4 – Virtual machine check for security updates from NEANIAS Nagios

4.5. Service reliability and availability

The *availability* and *reliability* of NEANIAS services is monitored by both the NEANIAS monitoring system (Nagios) and by ARGO, the EOSC monitoring service. As it is standard in service management, we focus on reliability, where planned and agreed interruptions (e.g., for maintenance) are not considered downtime since they are not part of the effective operating time, as already mentioned at deliverable D7.3 “Software Assessment Methodology” [2]. For reference, we consider availability as the percent available regardless of planned maintenance.

Reliability of NEANIAS services has reached about 99.9% as services were becoming more mature, as shown at the following figures.

During the project lifetime we encountered cases where the service reliability measurement was affected by network issues on the side of the monitoring services (NEANIAS Nagios, ARGO) while the monitored service was in fact available to its end users (globally or to some countries). Such errors are difficult to distinguish and may affect in some cases our reports.

The reliability is close to 99.9% (99.87% during October 2022) and, as shown in Figure 4.5 below, many of the services reached a value of 100%, which is considered a very high value, in accordance with what was planned at the beginning of the project. This is achieved without having any corporate contracts that would set that high availability requirements.

Figure 4.5 – Reliability per service for October 2022

The reliability in some cases is not 100% due to temporary infrastructure issues (network, power, hosts) or/and network issues across providers, which were unpredictable, and not related to actual services' problems.

4.6. Issues by external users

The NEANIAS Service Management System (SMS) provides metrics about the submitted tickets for every service. To present the external user activities we selected the access request tickets and the Figure 4.6 shows the submitted tickets per service by the external users. At this point, it is worth mentioning that although all NEANIAS services require authenticated user access, not all require explicit authorization for the service usage. These centrally managed authorization requests are the ones depicted below.

Figure 4.6.- Thematic service Access request tickets

Based on the SMS metrics, the average *turnaround time of the critical tickets* issued by the external users for every ticket type is **within one working day** for every Thematic service.

4.7. Turnaround time for issues initiated by NEANIAS internal users

Figure 4.7 presents the submitted Internal request tickets by the NEANIAS project members to every Core service and Critical ticket. For example, the Logging service used this ticket type for certification updates.

Figure 4.7. - Core service tickets

Figure 4.8 presents the average *first response time* (in days) per Core service. This time measures the elapsed time (in days) between the ticket submission and the first response time, when the ticket is changed to “Under investigation” status. For critical tickets (coming from internal users), the average *turnaround time* is **within one working day** for every Core service.

Figure 4.8. - Core service ticket first response time

4.8. Release cycle duration

Following up on the release cycle of the thematic services offered through NEANIAS, three major releases were planned to help reach the major milestones of each service. Still, it was expected that between these major releases, additional corrective and bug fixing releases, at minimum, would be needed. Through the Service Management processes defined and implemented, these releases were tracked to be able to report on the minor release cycle duration.

At this point, it is worth mentioning that since the initial activity planning [1] it was proposed that the Semantic Version scheme should be used for its simplicity and wide adaptation. What this scheme brings is that given a version number MAJOR.MINOR.PATCH, increment the:

- MAJOR version when you make incompatible API changes,
- MINOR version when you add functionality in a backwards compatible manner, and
- PATCH version when you make backwards compatible bug fixes.

And even though additional labels for pre-release and build metadata can be available as extensions to the MAJOR.MINOR.PATCH format, at least this common, base schema would be employed.

Figure 4.9.- Average release cycle duration

The above Figure 4.9.- Average release cycle duration presents the average *release cycle duration* for thematic services. The majority of the services had a low average release cycle of approximately 2 months. Across all the thematic services, the average of the minor releases cycle was 2.7 months.

5. Conclusions

This document, Deliverable D7.8 “Operation Activities Report (final)” has reported on the operation activities of the NEANIAS project and their operational performance from the point of view of the selected metrics and tools.

In particular, Section 2 has reported on the operation activities regarding service deployment environments, service deployment models and actual service operation and monitoring, section 3 has shown the evolution of services over time from a non-technical point of view, and Section 4 has focused on the reporting and analysis of the collected service metrics.

The operation activities in WP7 are one of the pillars which allows for the successful rollout of NEANIAS services to the targeted scientific communities. The use of state-of-the-art techniques, along with cloud-native and open tools is fundamental towards producing and operating high-quality services and achieving reproducibility. To this regard, we hope that NEANIAS has paved the way to the delivery of the EOSC services of the future.

References

- [1] NEANIAS Deliverable D7.1 “Delivery activities methodology and plan”
- [2] NEANIAS Deliverable D7.3 “Software assessment methodology”
- [3] NEANIAS Deliverable D7.4 “Infrastructures integration report (interim)”
- [4] NEANIAS Deliverable D7.5 “Operation Activities report (interim)”
- [5] NEANIAS Deliverable D7.7 “Infrastructures integration report”
- [6] Docker containers: <https://www.docker.com/>
- [7] LXC containers: <https://linuxcontainers.org/>
- [8] NEANIAS Deliverable D8.2 “EOSC service model report”
- [9] NEANIAS Catalogue: <https://catalogue.neanias.eu/home>
- [10] NEANIAS monitoring through EGI ARGO <https://neanias.ui.argo.grnet.gr/>
- [11] NEANIAS Deliverable D7.2 “Software delivery infrastructure and tools”
- [12] NEANIAS Deliverable D6.1 “Core services architecture, design principles and specifications report – Implementation Plan”
- [13] EGI ARGO EOSC integrated Monitoring – NEANIAS dashboard: <https://neanias.ui.devel.argo.grnet.gr/>
- [14] NEANIAS Deliverable D2.3 “Underwater Thematic Services Release #1”
- [15] NEANIAS Deliverable D2.5 “Underwater Thematic Services Release #2”
- [16] NEANIAS Deliverable D2.7 “Underwater Thematic Services Release #3”
- [17] NEANIAS Deliverable D2.8 “Report on the Developed and Validated Underwater Thematic Services #3”
- [18] NEANIAS Deliverable D3.3 “Atmospheric Thematic Services Release #1”
- [19] NEANIAS Deliverable D3.5 “Atmospheric Thematic Services Release #2”
- [20] NEANIAS Deliverable D3.7 “Atmospheric Thematic Services Release #3”
- [21] NEANIAS Deliverable D3.8 “Report on the Developed and Validated Atmospheric Thematic Services #3”
- [22] NEANIAS Deliverable D4.3 “Space Thematic Services Release #1”
- [23] NEANIAS Deliverable D4.5 “Space Thematic Services Release #2”
- [24] NEANIAS Deliverable D4.7 “Space Thematic Services Release #3”
- [25] NEANIAS Deliverable D4.8 “Report on the Developed and Validated Space Thematic Services #3”
- [26] NEANIAS Deliverable D6.2 “Core services Release #1”
- [27] NEANIAS Deliverable D6.4 “Core Services Architecture, Design Principles and Specifications Report – Implementation Plan (update)”
- [28] NEANIAS Deliverable D6.5 “Core services Release #2”
- [29] NEANIAS Deliverable D6.7 “Core services Release #3”
- [30] NEANIAS Deliverable D6.8 “Core services software release report #3”
- [31] NEANIAS Deliverable D8.5 “EOSC Integration Activities Report (final)”

List of acronyms

Acronym	Description
AAI	Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure
API	Application Programming Interface
CI/CD	Continuous Integration – Continuous Delivery
CRM	Customer Relationship Management
DNS	Domain Name System
GPU	Graphical Processing Unit
IaaS	Infrastructure as a Service
ICMP	Internet Control Message Protocol
ISRM	Incident and Service Request Management
FitSM	Family of Standards for lightweight IT Service Management
FQDN	Fully Qualified Domain Name
OIDC	OpenID Connect
NRPE	Nagios Remote Plugin Executor
PaaS	Platform as a Service
PKI	Public Key Infrastructure
RDM	Release and Deployment Management
SAML	Security Assertion Markup Language
SACM	Service Availability and Continuity Management
SLA	Service Level Agreement
SLM	Service Level Management
SMS	Service Management System
SPM	Service Portfolio Management
SLM	Service Level Management
VM	Virtual Machine